

Guidelines for Individuals and Communities (Including Research & Scientists) on Working from Home amid COVID-19, A CONFINEMENT ADAPTATION KIT

ĐIỀU KIỆN XÁC NHẬN: Bộ dụng cụ hành chính

COINNÍOLLACHA COMHDHLÚTHA KIT

محدود ہونے کے شرائط: موافقت کٹ

CONDIZIONE DI CONFINAMENTO: KIT DI ADATTAMENTO

CONDITION DE CONFINEMENT: KIT D'ADAPTATION

Confinement at home is in fact an effective procedure that is used to stop the spread of a virus particularly in pandemics. In spite it is effective, it brings negative consequences on individuals, the community and the economy, especially if the confinement is long and very restrictive. Experts in sociology, professionals in human behaviour and previous formal studies in human psychology can help to define and understand human thinking and human reactions and when applicable advice using medical procedures. However conditions of confinement under high levels of uncertainty are unique situations and combining them with work activities in order to be productive leads to very complex scenarios. Under these circumstances, where no well-defined procedures exist, like in COVID-19, it is normal to think that everybody is experimenting and implementing their own method(s) for confinement. Under these circumstances it is not difficult to imagine a solution where everybody can contribute to find a common way to preserve health, maintain family priorities and increase productivity for the duration of the confinement by describing describe their own way of work. We are presenting in this short document a method for confinement using multiple views and based on experiences, we contextualise the method to address the first and only question that in confinement at home circumstances in a pandemic people ask:

"How to successfully go into Confinement at Home?"

Today digital communication and the exchange of information is very fast, news that are generated in one part of the world can be shared almost instantaneously in other parts, there are also many channels for this i.e. printed and electronic, social networks etc. In health emergencies like a pandemic the communication process is very important, it may change the way that the pandemic is well addressed, in time or not. However, unfortunately it is also an opportunity for speculation and political interest. It is an opportunity for a lot of fake news and misinformation leading to a negative environment of confusion and misinformation. The first advice is not to believe all the information that is circulated but to go to reliable sources and contrast the information, do not simply pay attention but be critical and thus you can do your own assessment and have a good idea about what is happening, and possibly separate what is real from what is fake. This critical assessment requires trust on reliable sources and to avoid entering into the social networks information loop that can distract your attention.

The Preparation process for a Successful Confinement

Adapting quickly and efficiently to the procedures and recommendations indicated during a health emergency like a global pandemic is crucial not only for preserving personal health but also for having a good balance between family relationships and job responsibilities. The first fact that does not need to be explained is that in a health emergency (i.e. a breakout, an epidemic or a pandemic), the health system is the main point of concern. The second fact is that the risk in a health emergency is shared, this means that it is the responsibility of everyone to help in reducing the negative effects during and after the health emergency occurs. The third fact is that governments and health organisations are not responsible for the pandemic, but they help to be prepared, cope with the pandemic and manage the consequences. The fourth fact is that even if the pandemic looks like it is already under control, there is always a risk for new outbreaks, thus some of the procedures related to keep the health of individuals used to stop the pandemic shall be adopted for longer terms and the contingency methods shall be in place to prevent it. The last but not least fact is that in a global Pandemic, all efforts will never be enough to avoid and/or contain the escalation and it is extremely important to have good procedures for handling the effects.

Be prepare for a change in mind

On the society side, nobody expects that our daily routines and activities will change dramatically from one day to another and in particular, it is very difficult to imagine situations when all industry sectors, government organisations and societal groups are affected as a consequence of an epidemic outbreak.

These emergency situations are beyond many people's imagination and thus preparing the conditions for such scenario(s) where there is no short or mid-term visible solution is crucial. Beyond those health outbreaks other multiple circumstances could happen that require our life be redefined sometimes even overnight. i.e. Natural disasters, Human-driven Catastrophes and Social Instability or Wars.

Living Conditions and Lifestyle are going to be different

Health emergencies i.e. Epidemic Outbreaks, Epidemics or Pandemics are part of human history, and there is no indication this situation can change, particularly when urban spaces are rapidly gaining territory to natural spaces or when by means of human intervention the natural ecosystems and wild ecosystems are modified or altered. With the current outbreak of COVID-19, humanity is remembering that it is necessary to keep in mind that pandemics can drastically change the way we live. However beyond the importance of having awareness about the consequences of a global health emergency the most important issue is to have basic procedures and/or guidance to adapt quickly and efficiently to the new living conditions and thus reduce the effects that extreme situations, such as a pandemic may generate in individuals its surroundings and the society and their living spaces in general.

Dealing with the first effects of a confinement process

In a pandemic outbreak it is well known that all of society, organisations and basic industrial activities, also known as primary services industry, will continue in operation and focus on alleviating the effects of the health emergency by maintaining the basic services/needs. Many activities will be disrupted, and societies will be affected in their normal operation and their economies. In this panorama some general questions arise, what happened at the individual level? Is it possible to adapt rapidly and efficiently to those changes and conditions generated from a pandemic outbreak? How an individual and particularly one from the research and scientific community will be affected? and most importantly how to be better prepared? The answer to those questions is typically addressed in a variety of ways and depending on the circumstances and preferences of each individual sooner or later everybody shall adapt to the conditions and restrictions in life in the best possible way.

Having Good Communication and Take Wise decisions

Taking the assumption that preserving health is the most important and that health conditions must be the first priority in any pandemic outbreak. It is not difficult to think that the first responders are the ones dedicated to containing the situation and then mitigate the effects. It is also not difficult to think that the first points of attention are the public response units i.e. Health System, Emergency Units, Police Bodies and Military Forces on which rely a lot of responsibilities beyond the risk for them and their families that this implies. In cases like the COVID-19, where there is no pattern or an identified way to treat the virus that is generating the pandemic the research and scientific community is in first plane too and not only to investigate a possible cure but also to understand, finding procedures and identifying the causes, methods and possible solutions, all in a very short period of time. The important role of communicating quick results with the most accurate and valid information and the use of wise rationale and decisions are crucial in the scientific processes and similar to every individual in the society these conditions generates in each researcher and scientist at all levels, (i.e. junior, seniors or principal scientists) high levels of uncertainty and anxiety. Researchers and scientists can have high levels of stress by having big responsibilities not only for themselves and their activity but also for their families and for the society.

Be aware of unexpected things

It is well known that if good conditions exist for our daily activities, then better results for that activity are expected. Under conditions of confinement or Working from Home due to a pandemic outbreak the conditions may not be as they are planned or even expected. It is a reality that we are in a complex scenario, particularly if we want to achieve a good health balance and excellent results in our activities at work. Unexpected things will happen, there is definitely no defined method in a pandemic but best practices based on consensus and shared experiences and there is no more reliable source than your own expertise and good criteria who can guide you in uncertain periods. Add to your plans at working from home the fact that combining work and family under the same home space will always make both activities more complicated, however following a procedure may simplify this complexity.

The Proposed Method

In this short document we describe a methodology or procedure based on seven best practices, with the aim of using them as guidelines, that we all (including the research and scientific community) can use to start working from home efficiently, while continuing also to spend quality time with family in confinement situations. It also can serve to reassess your current confinement situation and rectify your procedures that most likely were generated on the fly with no guidance beyond your common sense. This document is the collection of individuals like you and their experience(s) in dealing with family issues and working from home. In COVID-19 pandemic confinement practical guidelines are now the most important procedures that we, the research and scientific community, can use and share with each other for our better adaptation and satisfactory living even after the confinement ends.

The Objective(s)

The following guidelines included in this document are just experiences and consensus of some ideas to start improving your adaptation for working from home without losing the family relationship and the social touch. If reading the guidelines is completely clear and understood and the included guidelines are executed in the suggested order, this document will help you in your process towards your confinement adaptation process, we have built this document based on shared experiences from members of our community in the form of:

- Self assessment for family aspects and work performance under confinement conditions.
- Definition of daily alternative routine during confinement conditions.
- Advice for activities on how to work from home during confinement situations.
- Defining your own method to combine family and work activities.
- Best ways for keeping the balance between family, work and health.
- Select your priorities during the WFH period without losing the work responsibilities.
- Understand the time you need to dedicate to yourself, family and work activities.

Confinement Adaptation Kit,

The 7 Key Confinement Recommendations:

In the following sections you can find information that can guide you or any other individuals that want to start their journey to confinement either for recommendation, necessity or by personal initiative. The order they are described and all the activities listed, shall be followed in order to run the confinement process. This information is made available with the objective of sharing experiences, being more effective and making sure that confinement conditions don't affect daily activities negatively. The information provided in the form of experiences and recommendations also aims to maintain our interpersonal conditions with family or the people with you are living and sharing common indoor spaces.

1 Understanding the Situation

The lack of scientific analysis or at least reliable evidence about the reason(s) that generated the health emergency i.e. pandemic outbreak, epidemic or pandemic always work negatively. The intention of this section is to explain that any individual willing to go successfully into a confinement adaptation process, first of all shall understand the context in relation to what is known from previous experiences and what are the previous measures that were taken as a result to alleviate the effects of a health break rather than early stage explanations. The following are some guidelines for better understanding of the situation:

- *Giving priority to the contextual information is a key for better understanding.*
- *Identifying sources of trusted and consistent information is a must to avoid panic.*
- *Check information from several trusted sources to ensure their concordance.*
- *Only follow up with official communications and trusted channels for better information.*
- *Reduce the use of social networks as a source for validating facts.*

2 Finding your place and your participation role

Similar to a clock machinery where every single piece plays a crucial role in the operation of the clock to provide the exact time, in a health emergency many activities and individual efforts will be required, identifying the proper place and level of participation is important. On this line it is important to understand that there will be front liners where individuals will be directly invited to participate, others will work in the background with similar or even more important functions than the front liners, and many others (majority) will remain performing the daily activities which are equally important than the others, simply because the outbreak circumstances are exceptional and keeping the day to day activities in continuous progress will help not only the mental health of individuals but also progress towards minimizing the side effects of the health emergency. The following are some guidelines for finding your place and define your participation role. Everybody plays an important role:

- *Understanding our personal role in any situation and under particular circumstances is best.*
- *Ensuring that the required tools and equipment are accessible to fulfil that role.*
- *Keeping information up to date to adapt your activities so they are still relevant.*
- *Ensure that the activities are relevant to the problem at hand.*
- *Thinking about the impact of your activity and not just the effects of the activity.*

3

Setting your temporal/semi-permanent working space

Every single person is by nature territorial, this means that it is necessary to have the feeling of belonging or owning a place, even if that feeling is temporary, this explains the importance of having an identified and delimited workspace. Having a dedicated workspace at home paying attention to the location and separation (even if it is within the same home space) facilitates that the mindset when entering that place, play a key role in the process of adapting to confinement conditions. In a personal workspace, each person must be able to separate activities and get the correct space to execute their work, sometimes a simple label or a symbol to differentiate the working spaces from other areas is a simple activity that can define a change in attitude and motivation to do activities more efficiently. The same principle applies to define other people's boundaries by indicating if access is allowed and the time frame(s) for this access. The following are some guidelines for setting up your working place:

- *Define a place where you can think differently, even for short periods, this is crucial.*
- *Make sure that other people in the home environment respect that space.*
- *All equipment concentrated in that space helps to minimise the risk of wandering.*
- *Insulate the space from noise and people transhumance (with very little people passage)*
- *Establish working time when you cannot be disturbed and times when you are freely accessible.*

4

Acting towards alleviating overload of good ideas and work

Everybody in the scientific community is full of ideas, in fact ideas are the main thing that characterizes a scientist. Ideas are the motivation and most of the time the main way to progress with new discoveries. Engineers are to inventions as scientists are to discoveries nevertheless the materialisation/implementation of an idea may imply both processes sometimes. It is a good practice in confinement conditions to be able to limit the number of ideas to prevent overloading of the discovery or simply losing the objective of derived activities that need to be performed during the confinement.

The following are some guidelines to reduce the overload of good ideas:

- *Ideas are necessary to keep motivation but limit them to be able to address the objectives that are defined by your work and original activities before the confinement.*
- *It is necessary to consciously develop a new routine to manage the required workload and pay attention to address the new idea(s), perhaps have an ideas time in the mornings only.*
- *Keep the new routine as close to the structure of the old routine and avoid mixing with current activities and define time frames to work on the ideas separately.*
- *Make sure that the new ideas are relevant to the assigned activities and*
- *Do not interfere with old ideas already implemented and look forward to the new work.*

5

Proactivity keeping balance between personal and professional activities

Moving to work in your personal space(s) is something very challenging. In the last two decades the working from home scheme has become popular. This voluntary or forced move has to be done consciously, not only because of the fact that physical space restrictions may exist i.e. size of the room or because of inadequate types of furniture or surroundings but also because of family relationship(s) or sharing space, all of these need to be adequate. The implications of working from home can affect the productivity and motivation of your work, positive or negative independently on what kind of people you are, (i.e. type 1) a person that considers working is necessary for living or type 2) people that consider working is life). Two facts that working from home will definitely change, firstly the time you can or cannot dedicate to other people, and secondly you will need to define your strategy and philosophy for working, involving the member(s) of your family or other people sharing space with you. The following are guidelines towards keeping balance between personal and professional activities at home:

- *Define a daily routine (start-end time) and follow it as if you are working at the office.*
- *Select and define the priorities, but it is highly advisable that personal stands out over work.*
- *Develop methods to respect the requirements of others who live with you.*
- *Talk with other people who are also working remotely to have concurrent working hours to limit the strain on the non-working people.*
- *Assign time for you and your family and define your priorities based on their demands and always try keeping a good atmosphere at home and a tidy place for work.*
- *Positive results will only happen if personal issues are first resolved then work issues.*

6

Maintaining your social touch with colleagues and people

The implications of being confined at home by a pandemic with restrictions of mobility in place and the uncertainty generated by the restrictions of access to bars, restaurants and industries influence the way we feel and live. All in all the flow of information and misinformation influence the way we perceive the COVID-19 pandemic confinement. Something certain is that confinement is an effective procedure to stop a pandemic, under which normal changes in our humour occur, feelings and sensibility (mostly negative) to external agents will occur more frequently putting the nerves (even of the most stable person) to the limit. There are numerous references to professional methodologies and therapies on how to manage the sensibility and stress effects. In extreme cases of stress and anxiety the help of professionals in human conduct is required. However in confinement conditions it is important to consider that in no other place you and your loved ones will be better, restrictions to mobility and being confined if not isolated, in some cases may influence very negatively, particularly if you are alone and do not have people surrounding you. However even in those conditions staying at home is the best way to help yourself and many other people and it also should be considered that at any time the anxiety may increase. The following are guidelines for maintaining your social contact with colleagues and other people:

- *Exercise positive communication practices by being in touch regularly with relatives.*

- Prepare yourself by dressing up as normal (even if it is only half body up) is important.
- Video conference at least once a week with unit colleagues and close friends using video.
- Chat and conference calls are important, use them less frequently for other colleagues and friends and not necessarily through video sharing (phone calls, emails, texts, etc.)
- Use those opportunities to exchange funny experiences and avoid talking on COVID-19

7

Redefine activities and priorities

Having a plan of activities and prioritising them is important and this can help to reduce the effects amid a health emergency. However planning is an important activity it is not always easy to do specially during a period of high uncertainty or where the procedures to have a controlled situation are not well defined. Having the flexibility to change plans and priorities is always a positive element to act positively, there will be some activities and objectives that cannot be moved, delayed or changed, however those that can be moved need to be well identified in order to have the capacity to move them as desired. A good practice is to set in first order activities that can be resolved fast (even if they are not critical in the plan) first be confident that if an emergency happen the plans can be moved or delayed thus at least you will have those activities done, then set in second plane the activities that demands more efforts, because working full time from home will give you an advantage to have work done that cannot be affected by a health emergency and then the last is that work that need special equipment like in a laboratory for later. Thus while the main priority will be to resolve those activities and tasks that require it to be done imminently delay those activities that demand more time to be done or that require special equipment. The following are guidelines for redefining activities and priorities:

- Health is first, during an health emergency, list all your activities and identify priorities
- Family is first and first priority to work activities rely on activities that can be resolved fast
- My work is first under full time working from home if it can be done remotely.
- Activities that are priority under working conditions may be delayed in a health emergency.
- Be aware to be able to adapt to new circumstances due to the evolving information.

Final Comments

- Confinement at home as result of a health alerts is a procedure to alleviate and stop the effect of spread of virus or a disease in a health outbreak, as result of this working from home schemes and procedures are necessary to be defined and take place.
- The use of a methodology for confinement defining clear steps as check points for working from home conditions is important particularly to minimize the effects of negative impacts on health and work productivity.
- Confinement at home is an effective procedure that is used to stop the spread of a virus in a pandemic. The World health organisation (WHO) and other health organisations worldwide includes this method in all their procedures, confinement at home will generate individual

anxiety, social instability and economic effects, It is the responsibility of every member of the society actively follow recommendations and procedures from official sources with the objective to get accurate information and reduce personal unhealthy circumstances.

- To minimise the effects of a health emergency, not everybody has to get involved in front line activities, but try to keep a positive attitude and find your role and responsibilities. It is important to engage in the official activities and prioritise health-related ones taking always into consideration that any other activities will have an impact and that also the economy will be affected.
- Mental health is equally important and need proper attention as the effects in a pandemic where high levels of stress and anxiety are present. Remaining socially connected will reduce the negative mental health effects of isolation or Confinement.
- It is important to follow a procedure for self-quarantine when symptoms appear and follow basic procedures for isolation in order to protect not only our health but others.
- Groups and communities that are dependent of caregivers and health systems are in first line to get services to maintain routines, promote activity and get their meal.
- Socially distancing is a practice that is important to exercise not only during the initial phases of COVID-19 emergency health but also during the de-escalation phase in order to prevent new health outbreaks.

Disclaimer and Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the scientific community and active researchers for their participation and inputs provided to create and validate this document alike the feedback received. The main purpose of this document is to be used as support for going into the process of self-isolation, self-quarantine and/or confinement and eventually every individual with the correct understanding and application of normal criteria adapts your own methodology based on **The 7 Key Confinement Recommendations** introduced and explained in this short document.

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It is important to highlight that any official information and recommendations provided from official sources must be followed and this document does not interfere or surpass any official information provided by any of the health institutions, organisations or governmental authorities in your country, state or your local area.

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March 2020